

T40, I'm calling it that way because it sounds cool.

This is an old version of my theory and there are some flaws in it. I really can't write a new one without getting angry at what I write because it all sounds wrong. The Keyword here is "Negative". Just so you know that this isn't a single theory it's basically an ecosystem and all of my theories somehow end up on the same thing: "Negative" and I'm not talking about physics or math but literally everything to life, awareness, space I mean, you name it. My brain for some reason likes to predict what I'll write in the future, it's like a pattern recognition super computer.

This is one of my many theories but I guess this one is more tangible than the others. I wrote this when I was 13 so I modified it a little bit so it might be clearer to understand.

Here it is..

(all according to my old notebook)

If there's negative numbers, can't there be a negative Universe?

We made Quantum Computers capable of simulating negative realities, and if we think about it, Quantum Computers are somewhat alive and need specific conditions to do whatever is told.

Same with Quantum particles.

And that could give us an idea.

If positive exists, negative has to exist otherwise there would be a very catastrophic result.

And what if we tried to visualize it or even better use it? but we must get an understanding of it.

And that's how it all started.. The second I wrote this, a thought came into my mind. What about cubes?

The Cube

Imagine a square, a hollow one (2D). if I want it to be in a negative version (inside-out), it won't change at all. Why? well. Let's take a hat and if we push inwards the top it will eventually be somewhat inside-out, why? because it has space to modify itself.

since it needs space to change but our square doesn't have any hollow lines, nothing changes.

But instead of a 2D square. What if it was 3D? the lines don't move but the inside does. which is space.

Just like a hat.

I suck at math horribly. But I hope it'll make sense.

If + × = Bigger

If % - = Smaller

Then it means there's something in between these. Something that does both at the same time. What could it be? What would the something be if we translated it into a shape? Is it infinity? a black hole? Quantum mechanics? Zero? Sure there must be a sort of balancer between these two, i'll leave the question for you to answer.

Examples

The Fourth dimension is a negative number. Just like pants, you make them inside-out. (the inside is now outside).

1. Large cube + small cube inside + 8 connecting lines, (not showing them, but imagine it)

2. After one inversion a small cube is now outside, and a large cube collapsed inside.

Like I've explained before, 1D lines cannot be modified or inverted.

Lets place a smaller cube inside a bigger one and we connect each side or vertices with the eight lines.

- When the bigger cube is inverted through its faces, the smaller cube (lets call it inner cube) is forced outward which then becomes the new bigger cube.
- Because nothing is telling it to stop, it will never stop. But why does this loop happen? Take an example of magnets, if we do the same thing with the magnets it's forced to repeat this loop no matter what because there isn't a stopping or original point where a line or the cube can stop or rest.

This is the Tesseract for me.

One extra detail: after the first inversion the stuff is the same to the starting position with the cubes swapped. It's just like breathing.

This was a bit of my many theories, this was relatively simple than the others, if you wanna know anything then im open to it. I just wanna help this damned world change somehow.

Stephen.